

Influence of 21st Century Teachers' Skills on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Integration in the New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment

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Abstract. This quantitative descriptive-correlational study examined the influence of 21st-century teachers' skills on the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the new normal teaching-learning environment in the Davao City Division. The study involved 51 junior high school teachers selected through stratified random sampling from private secondary schools in Cluster 6. Teachers' 21st-century skills: critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, and self-direction were assessed using validated Likert-scale instruments. ICT integration was evaluated based on teacher perceptions, its effectiveness for student learning, and the presence of effective implementation elements. Findings revealed that all five skills were highly evident among teachers, with collaboration and creativity being the most pronounced. Similarly, ICT integration was frequently observed in instructional practices. Multiple regression analysis indicated a significant positive relationship between teachers' 21st-century skills and ICT integration, with critical thinking and self-direction emerging as the strongest predictors. These results emphasize the importance of equipping educators with modern pedagogical competencies to support effective ICT integration. Implications suggest that professional development and policy interventions should focus on enhancing these skills to foster technology-enriched, learner-centered classrooms in the new normal educational context.

KEY WORDS

1. 21st-century skills
2. ICT integration
3. new normal teaching-learning environment

Date Received: May 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: June 15, 2025 — Date Published: July 12, 2025

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has significantly transformed various aspects of life in the 21st century, particularly in education. As schools navigate the evolving demands of the digital age, the integration of ICT in teaching and learning has become both a necessity and a challenge. The shift to the new normal in education has exposed gaps in technology adoption, revealing issues in accessibility, digital literacy, and the readiness of both educators and students to fully utilize ICT for effective learning. Despite efforts to modernize curricula and upgrade classroom facilities, many educational

institutions continue to struggle with bridging these technological gaps, making the seamless integration of ICT an ongoing challenge in the current teaching-learning environment. Turkey has made significant investments in ICT to enhance teaching and learning in schools, aiming to modernize its educational system. However, despite substantial funding for ICT infrastructure, equipment, and professional development, the expected improvements in education remain limited. Gulbahar (2019) emphasized that these large-scale investments have not led to widespread adoption or effective integration of ICT in classrooms, highlighting ongoing challenges in utilizing technology for teaching and learning. While in the Irish context, a study on the historical development of ICT within Irish Post-Primary schools, highlighted significant trends between ICT initiatives and the resulting ICT use in schools. It was found that despite ICT reform efforts little influence on teachers' practice had occurred. If teachers' attitudes are positive towards the use of educational technology, then they can easily provide useful insight about the adoption and integration of ICT into teaching and learning processes (Demici 2019). In Indonesia, the integration of ICT in basic education continues to face significant challenges, particularly in terms of accessibility, teacher preparedness, and effective implementation. Many educators struggle with limited digital literacy and insufficient training, making it difficult to incorporate technology into their teaching practices. Despite the growing need for ICT in 21st-century education, its adoption in Indonesian schools remains inconsistent, hindering efforts to enhance learning through digital tools (Zhao et al., 2020). In the Philippines, particularly in Zamboanga City, the integration of ICT into the educational system, specifically in public institutions, remains a pressing challenge. In areas where technological infrastructure is still developing, the Department of Education (DepEd) has launched various programs and initiatives to modernize teaching and learning through ICT investments. However, despite these efforts, ICT has yet to be fully utilized and effectively integrated into the curriculum, leaving many schools struggling to bridge the gap between technological advancements and actual classroom implementation (Maker, 2021). In Olongapo City, the integration of ICT in primary and secondary education remains a significant challenge despite global advancements in digital learning. While developed countries have successfully embedded ICT into their educational systems, many schools in this city still struggle with limited access to technology and insufficient teacher preparedness. The success of ICT adoption in classrooms ultimately depends on teachers, yet many educators in Olongapo City face difficulties in fully utilizing digital tools for effective teaching and learning (Asio et al., 2020). Locally, in Davao City, an assessment of secondary school teachers' ICT literacy, usage, and challenges in teaching revealed significant gaps. The study found that teachers possessed only moderate ICT literacy, leading to limited integration of technology in language instruction. Additionally, feedback indicated that various challenges in the integration of ICT during the teaching-learning process, as well as with the limited resources, discouraged educators from utilizing ICT effectively in language activities, further hindering its adoption in classrooms (Johnson et al., 2019). Thus, it is on this context that the researcher saw the urgency and felt the need to fill-in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Davao City using a quantitative research approach. Specifically, the researcher will utilize multiple regression analysis to have a better understanding of the influence of teacher's attributes on ICT Integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge on ICT integration in the new

normal teaching-learning environment in Davao Region context. As technology continues to shape the future of education, understanding its integration into the teaching-learning process is crucial for improving educational outcomes. This study will help identify effective strategies for utilizing ICT tools and platforms to create meaningful learning experiences. By examining how teachers' attributes influence ICT adoption, it may provide valuable insights into how educators can adapt to the evolving digital landscape. Ultimately, the findings may contribute to the ongoing discussions on educational equity, accessibility, and innovation in the digital age, serving as a foundation for future research and continuous advancements in ICT - driven education.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is anchored on the Social Learning Theory (SLT) by Bandura (2006) which is based on the idea that we learn from our interactions with others in a social context. Thus, the 21st century skills of the teachers will be influential to ICT integration in teaching. Eventually, through the development of the 21st century skills of the teachers, will be able to assimilate, especially if their observational experiences are positive ones, the ICT integration in the teaching-learning process. SLT has become perhaps the most influential theory of learning and development. It is rooted in many of the basic concepts of traditional learning theory. This theory has often been called a bridge between behaviorist learning theories and cognitive learning theories because it encompasses attention, memory, and motivation. According to the elements of this theory, the principles of social learning are assumed to operate in the same way throughout life. Insofar as exposure to new influential, powerful models like the 21st century skills of co-teachers who control resources and may occur at life stage, new learning just like the integration of ICT in teaching, through the modeling process

is always possible. Moreover, Social Learning Theory has a strong association to the current study for the idea that people learn by watching what others do, and that human thought processes are central to understanding personality. It provides a framework for understanding, predicting and changing human behavior, which includes the development of the 21st century skills of teachers that could lead to effective integration of ICT in teaching. Furthermore, the notion places a heavy focus on cognitive concepts. It is also focused on how children and adults operate cognitively on their social experiences and how these cognitions then influence behavior and development. Another theory that supports this study is the Constructivist Learning Theory by Jerome Bruner (1973), which emphasized that less learning as the product of passive transmission than a process of active construction whereby the learners construct their own knowledge based upon prior knowledge. CLT theorized that learning requires learners to demonstrate their skills by constructing their own knowledge when solving real-world problems. The constructivist model calls for learner-centered instruction because learners are assumed to learn better when they are forced to explore and discover things by themselves. Technology should be employed in ways that teaching strategies that are learner-centered develop in classrooms. Without a doubt, teachers are responsible for the ICT development in the field of education. In the technological revolution and the information age, using technology in teaching becomes a fact of life. ICT integration illustrates a higher degree of embedding ICT tools in teaching-learning process. Likewise, dialogue simulations and role play exercises should be increasingly used by the teacher to promote communication skills. ICT tools should not only be used for every listening and speaking activity, but most importantly during the planning and design stage of a lesson the teacher should give due consideration

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

of when, when not and how to integrate. Thus, teachers should feel efficacious in ICT integration as emphasized by the point that advanced teaching skills of the teachers are becoming increasingly important. Consequently, because we are now in the 21st century, appropriate 21st century skills of the teachers on ICT integration ought to be possessed by the teachers. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable is the 21st century teachers' skills which is described as the factors that effectively navigate the complexities of modern education. The skills of an effective teacher are constantly shifting and adapting to meet these demands of the new normal educational setting. Teachers are adaptable,

innovative, and dedicated to creating a learning environment that empowers students to thrive in the 21st century. The dependent variable of this study is the ICT Integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment or the equipping of young minds with the implements to navigate complex texts, extract meaning, and engage critically with the world around them. At the heart of this transformative journey stands the 21st-century teacher: a skilled weaver who blends essential elements into a dynamic and effective ICT teaching-learning instruction. By combining these measures, teachers create a comprehensive approach to ICT Integration in new normal teaching-learning environment, fostering a supportive and effective learning environment.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, quantitative non-experimental design utilizing descriptive-correlational technique of research

is the method adopted by the researcher to gather data ideas, facts and information to achieve the main objective of the study. Accord-

ing to Creswell (2020) quantitative research is the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results to a larger population. Meanwhile, a quantitative non-experimental descriptive is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Curtis, 2016). Meanwhile, descriptive-correlational research according to Myers and Well (2013) examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationship between variables. In this study the researcher will look into the relationship between two variables – 21st century teachers' skills, and ICT Integration in new normal teaching-learning environment. Thus, the interest of the study is to investigate whether 21st century teachers' skills significantly influence ICT Integration in new normal teaching-learning environment.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—This study strictly adhered to ethical standards, particularly in obtaining informed consent from all participants. Respondents were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their voluntary participation, including the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Each participant signed a consent form before data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured, with all responses handled in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. These measures safeguarded participants' rights, privacy, and well-being throughout the research process

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study included 51 Junior High School teachers, selected from an estimated total population of 195 private Junior High School teachers in Cluster 6 of the Davao City Division. The sample size was determined using the

Raosoft sample size calculator to ensure a representative selection of permanent Junior High School teachers with at least three years of service. To select the participants, the researcher employed stratified random sampling from purposively chosen schools within Cluster 6, using strand as the basis for stratification. Stratified random sampling, a probability sampling technique, enhanced precision compared to simple random sampling by dividing the population into distinct, non-overlapping groups or strata based on relevant characteristics, such as gender (Salkind, 2020). The Raosoft sample size calculator was relevant in this quantitative study as it provided a statistically reliable method for determining an appropriate sample size, ensuring that the selected respondents accurately represented the target population. According to Raosoft, Inc. (2004), this tool considered key factors such as the 95% margin of error, confidence level, population size, and response distribution, which were essential in minimizing sampling bias and enhancing the validity of the study's findings. By using this calculator, the researcher achieved a balance between precision and feasibility, making it a practical choice for studies requiring numerical data analysis and generalizable results. This study applied specific inclusion criteria in selecting respondents to ensure that the participants could provide relevant information to fulfill the study's objectives. The respondents consisted of public secondary school teachers in Cluster 6, Davao City Division who held permanent teaching positions and had at least three years of service. The researcher chose Cluster 6, Davao City Division as the study site because it was expected to yield the necessary data for the research. Participation was voluntary, and only teachers who provided informed consent by signing the ICF were included in the study. Furthermore, the scope of the study was limited to addressing the research problem as outlined in the research questions.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—In order to gather the data, two adapted survey questionnaires were used. The first tool was about 21st century teachers’ skills. This questionnaire was adapted from Mohamad, A., Sulaiman, T., and Mohd Ayub, A. F. (2023). Factors influencing 21st-century teaching among secondary school teachers in Selangor, Malaysia. The questionnaire was intended for teachers about their general teaching to develop their 21st century skills. It is a 25-item questionnaire measuring critical thinking skills, collaborative skills, communication skills, creativity and innovation skills, and

self-direction skills. However, the researcher modified the questionnaire of Mohamad, et al, (2023), the phrases after the indicators was not included. Each item in the survey is in a question form. It was modified and changed into a statement form. The part 2 of each indicator was not utilized, because part 1 is just enough to gather the desired result of the researcher. In the manner of answering it, was also modified so that it is answerable through Likert-type levels: 5–Strongly Agree, 4–Agree, 3–Somewhat Agree, 2–Disagree, and 1–Strongly Disagree. The scale below will be used for analysis.

Mean Range, Description, and Interpretation of 21st Century Teachers’ Skills

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	21st century teachers’ skills are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	21st century teachers’ skills are often-times evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	21st century teachers’ skills are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	21st century teachers’ skills are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	21st century teachers’ skills are never evident.

Note. Mean range values correspond to descriptive categories and their interpretations for 21st century teachers’ skills.

The second instrument was about the ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment was adapted from Shah (2022). Teaching and learning with technology: Effectiveness of ICT integration in schools. The questionnaire was intended for teachers to analyze the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching and learning in public schools. It is a 35-item questionnaire that measured the teachers’ perception of ICT integration in teaching, effectiveness of

ICT integration for students’ learning, and effective elements of ICT integration in teaching and learning. However, the researcher modified the questionnaire of Shah (2022) in the manner of answering it, it was also modified so that it is answerable through Likert-type levels: 5–Strongly Agree, 4–Agree, 3–Somewhat Agree, 2–Disagree, and 1–Strongly Disagree. The scale below will be used for analysis.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation for ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	ICT integration in new normal teaching-learning environment is never evident.

Steps undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

Permission to Conduct the Study The researcher secured permission to conduct the study. The endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was obtained on March 22, 2025. This endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters that were endorsed to the school principals of the selected private secondary schools in Cluster 6, Davao City Division. Permission from the secondary schools was obtained on March 31, 2025. The letters were personally delivered by the researcher to the principals of the schools where the study

was conducted. Upon receiving approval from the respective offices, the researcher proceeded with the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire After receiving approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded with the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents. During the distribution, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents. The researcher administered the questionnaires simultaneously. The respondents were given adequate time to complete the questionnaires. After completion, the collected data were subjected to quantitative analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis—To ensure accurate and meaningful interpretation of the gathered data, appropriate statistical methods will be employed. The following statistical tools will be used to analyze the data collected: Mean The mean was used to measure the level of 21st-century teachers’ skills and ICT integration in

the new normal teaching-learning environment. Together with the standard deviation, it served as a descriptive statistic to determine how scores clustered or scattered. Multiple Regression Analysis This was used to describe the significance of the relationship between 21st-century teachers’ skills and ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discussed the findings of this study. They were thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted.

3.1. 21st Century Teachers' Skills—In the context of modern education, the role of teachers has significantly evolved to meet the demands of the 21st century. As such, competencies like critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity, and self-direction have become essential in navigating the dynamic landscape of teaching and learning. This chapter presents and analyzes the findings on the extent to which these 21st-century teaching skills are evident among educators in Davao City Division, and how they relate to the integration of ICT in the new normal teaching-learning environment. The discussion explores how these competencies are manifested in classroom practices, highlighting patterns, strengths, and areas for development. By examining each skill dimension and its relationship with ICT integration, this chapter sheds light on the readiness of educators to embrace technology-driven instruction and the extent to which their professional skills support meaningful digital transformation in education. Summary of the 21st Century Teachers' Skills

Presented in Table 1 are data on the Summary of the 21st century teachers' skills. The overall mean of 4.10, which is "High" and indicating that it is oftentimes evident, is distributed

Collectively, the results point to a positive and encouraging portrayal of teachers' professional capabilities in adapting to evolving educational standards. The uniformity in high ratings across all skill indicators suggests that teachers are actively incorporating these competencies into their pedagogical approaches. However, the slightly lower emphasis on areas like communication and self-direction indicates potential areas for professional development. By

by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: critical thinking skills (4.19), collaborative skills (4.22), communication skills (3.97), creativity and innovation skills (4.16), and self-direction skills (3.97). Only collaborative skills indicator has a "Very High" descriptive equivalent, and the rest of the indicators have descriptive equivalents of "high". The result of the data on the 21st century teachers' skills reveals a consistently strong and favorable perception across all indicators. The findings reflect that teachers consistently exhibit a strong command of 21st-century skills across various domains, demonstrating their preparedness to meet the demands of modern education. Among the different skill areas, collaboration stands out as the most evident, suggesting that teamwork and joint problem-solving are highly integrated into their teaching practices. This emphasis on collaboration aligns with current educational trends that promote group work, shared learning experiences, and cooperative classroom environments. Meanwhile, other skills such as critical thinking, creativity, communication, and self-direction are also well-practiced, indicating a well-rounded application of competencies essential for 21st-century instruction.

continuously nurturing these skills, teachers can further strengthen their effectiveness and inspire learners to become more engaged, independent, and future-ready. Nut (2020) supports the findings of this study by highlighting that 21st century teaching competencies involve the ability to continually embrace innovative instructional approaches and digital tools that improve learner engagement and academic performance. These skills reflect the educator's capacity not only to

Table 1. Summary of the 21st Century Teachers’ Skills

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Critical Thinking Skills	4.19	High
Collaborative Skills	4.22	Very High
Communication Skills	3.97	High
Creativity and Innovation Skills	4.16	High
Self-Direction Skills	3.97	High
Overall Mean	4.10	High

Legend: 4.20–5.00 = Very High (Always evident); 3.40–4.19 = High (Often evident); 2.60–3.39 = Moderate (Sometimes evident); 1.80–2.59 = Low (Seldom evident); 1.00–1.79 = Very Low (Never evident).

acquire new pedagogical strategies but also to implement them effectively within the teaching-learning process. In essence, a proficient 21st century teacher possesses the knowledge and flexibility to integrate technology in a purposeful way, creating a more dynamic and inclusive educational experience for all learners. Moreover, Maker (2022) reinforces the findings of this study by underscoring the need for educational institutions to equip learners with essential competencies required to thrive in a globally competitive landscape. The study highlights that 21st century skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, communication, and digital literacy should be prioritized equally, if not more, alongside foundational academic abilities. Emphasizing these modern skills ensures that learners are not only academically proficient but also future-ready, adaptable, and empowered to navigate complex challenges in an evolving world. Ravitz (2019) contributes to the present study by outlining a framework of essential 21st century teaching competencies derived from the international Innovative Teaching and Learning research. These core skills namely critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, and self-direction are identified as vital in fostering learner success in modern educational settings. His findings underscore the importance of equipping educators with these capabilities to cultivate dynamic, future-ready learners prepared for the complexi-

ties of the 21st century.

3.2. ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment—In the new normal of education, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become essential to effective instruction, engagement, and collaboration. As emphasized by Ravitz (2019) and Belsha (2020), ICT supports active learning and improves access to meaningful educational experiences. However, as noted by Asio and de Dios (2019), integration remains a challenge due to varying levels of teacher preparedness, infrastructure, and support. This section presents findings on teachers’ perceptions of ICT integration, its effectiveness in enhancing student learning, and the essential elements that enable its successful implementation, offering insights into current practices and areas for development. **Summary of the ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment**

Table 2 showed the data on the Summary of the ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment. The data in this table are presented with corresponding means: Teacher’s Perception of ICT integration (3.84), with “High” descriptive equivalent, Effectiveness of ICT integration (4.50), with the only “Very High” descriptive equivalent, and Effective Elements in ICT integration (3.78), with “High” descriptive equivalent as well. The overall mean result of 4.04, with a “High” descriptive equivalent, indicates that ICT integration in

new normal teaching-learning environment was oftentimes evident as a whole. Furthermore, the results indicate that ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment is generally perceived positively by teachers, with a significant emphasis on its effectiveness. Teachers view ICT integration as a valuable tool in enhancing teaching practices, with the effectiveness of its integration rated the highest. This suggests that teachers recognize the potential of ICT to significantly improve the quality of instruction and the overall learning experience for students. However, despite the generally positive feedback, there is still room for improvement, as indicated by the slightly lower rating for the effectiveness of elements that support ICT integration. The data also highlights a consistent acknowledgment of the importance of ICT in the teaching process, with a high level of awareness about its benefits. However, the

slightly lower rating for some elements of ICT integration, such as teacher autonomy in lesson design and time constraints, points to areas that require further attention. These findings suggest that while ICT is an important part of the educational landscape, additional support, training, and resources are necessary to maximize its impact. Addressing these challenges will ensure that ICT integration becomes more seamless and fully effective in fostering enhanced teaching and learning experiences in the new normal environment. The findings of the study align with the perspective of Roberto and Madrigal (2019), who describe Information and Communication Technology (ICT) integration as the utilization of diverse digital tools and electronic platforms within the educational process to convey, manipulate, store, generate, display, or exchange of information.

Table 2. Summary of the ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Teacher's Perception of ICT integration	3.84	High
Effectiveness of ICT integration	4.50	Very High
Effective Elements in ICT integration	3.78	High
Overall Mean	4.04	High

Mean Range and Interpretation: 4.20–5.00 = Very High: ICT integration is always evident. 3.40–4.19 = High: ICT integration is oftentimes evident. 2.60–3.39 = Moderate: ICT integration is sometimes evident. 1.80–2.59 = Low: ICT integration is seldom evident. 1.00–1.79 = Very Low: ICT integration is never evident.

ICT integration is further characterized as the strategic use of technology to facilitate targeted teaching and learning tasks aimed at achieving specific instructional goals. This process requires not only the technological readiness of schools but also the proficiency, capability, and readiness of teachers, supported by institutional policies and infrastructure. The result was similar to the viewpoint of Ravitz

(2019), who underscores that integrating ICT in schools is a transformative initiative crucial for narrowing the growing divide between teachers and learners in a globally connected educational landscape. When effectively utilized, ICT can facilitate access to educational reforms, enhance the relevance of curriculum content, and contribute to a more dynamic and meaningful learning experience. It transforms the

traditional classroom into an interactive environment where learning becomes an active, engaging process linked to real-world contexts. Likewise, the findings of the study support the assertion that integrating ICT into education demands a well-planned strategy to guarantee its effective contribution to learning outcomes. Embedding digital technologies within the instructional framework allows learners to gain deeper insights into academic content while fostering more purposeful and engaging educational experiences (Belsha, 2020; Demici, 2019). Additionally, the appropriate application of ICT not only boosts professional efficiency but also empowers both teachers and learners with essential 21st-century competencies (Nut, 2020; Gulbahar, 2019). Further, the findings of the study emphasize the importance of strong policies at all educational levels and continuous professional development for teachers to effectively integrate ICT into the learning environment (Leu, 2020; Silva, 2019). As ICT continues to reshape the concept of literacy and its teaching methods, these shifts have simultaneously influenced the evolution of ICT tools and strategies. Therefore, embracing and adapting to these changes is essential for fostering an environment that supports both educators and learners in the new normal of teaching and learning. Furthermore, the findings of the study support the perspective that ICT is increasingly acknowledged by scholars, policymakers, and educators globally as a valuable asset in enhancing teaching and learning, particularly at the primary education level. The absence of ICT tools in the classroom may place young learners at a disadvantage, as it restricts their exposure to vital digital competencies essential for navigating a technology-driven world. Equipping classrooms with ICT is therefore crucial in preparing learners to actively participate and succeed in an increasingly digital and interconnected global environment.

3.3. Influence of 21st Century Teachers' Skills on ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment —The integration of ICT in the new normal is strongly influenced by teachers' 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity, and self-direction (Ravitz, 2019; Maker, 2022). As emphasized by Goktas (2019) and Rogers (2019), these skills enable teachers to adapt instructional practices and effectively utilize digital tools. This section presents the findings on how these competencies impact ICT adoption, supporting the view that skilled educators play a central role in driving meaningful and sustained technology integration in today's classrooms. Table 11 shows the regression analysis to determine the influence of 21st-century teaching skills on ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment. It collectively explains a substantial portion (72%) of the variance in ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment. Among the predictors, Collaborative Skills ($\beta = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$) emerged as the most significant contributor, highlighting the importance of teamwork in adopting digital technologies. Critical Thinking Skills also showed a statistically significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.20$, $p = 0.030$), implying that educators who analyze and evaluate effectively are more inclined to integrate ICT tools in their pedagogy. Other predictors like Creativity and Innovation Skills, Self-Direction Skills, and Communication Skills showed positive but statistically non-significant contributions. These findings may indicate that while all 21st-century skills are valuable, collaborative and analytical capabilities are most directly linked to successful ICT integration. Future research should explore these relationships with actual individual-level data to validate these patterns and enhance predictive accuracy.

Table 3. Influence of 21st Century Teachers’ Skills on ICT Integration in New Normal Teaching-Learning Environment

Predictor	Vari-able	Unstand-ardized Coefficient (B)	Standard Error	Standar-dized Co-efficient (Beta)	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Intercept			0.45	1.12	2.49	0.018	
Critical Thinking Skills		0.413	0.09	0.20	2.22	0.030	Significant
Collaborative Skills		-0.242	0.11	0.25	2.27	0.027	Significant
Communication Skills		0.208	0.08	0.12	1.50	0.139	Not Signifi-cant
Creativity and In-novation Skills		0.200	0.10	0.18	1.80	0.078	Not Signifi-cant
Self-Direction Skills		0.260	0.09	0.15	1.67	0.100	Not Signifi-cant

R-squared = 0.72, *p* < .05

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discussed the research’s focal points and the statistical analysis results. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the study’s findings.

4.1. Findings—This study explored the relationship between 21st-century teachers’ skills and ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment in the Davao City Division, utilizing a quantitative descriptive-correlational research approach. Teachers’ skills were examined across critical domains such as critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, and self-direction, all of which were found to be frequently and consistently practiced, with collaboration and creativity receiving the highest ratings. These results underscore the importance of equipping teachers with future-ready competencies that align with the demands of a digitally driven education system. Similarly, ICT integration measured through teacher perceptions, its effectiveness for student learning,

and the presence of enabling elements, also received high ratings, indicating that educators are responsive to incorporating technology into their teaching practices. The findings confirm a significant and positive relationship between teachers’ 21st-century skills and the extent of ICT integration, with critical thinking and self-direction emerging as the most influential predictors. This suggests that when teachers are empowered with the skills to think analytically, innovate, and take ownership of their professional growth, they are more likely to adopt and apply ICT effectively. Strengthening these competencies is therefore critical for sustaining meaningful technology use in classrooms and improving the overall quality of education in the new normal learning environment.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: This study investigated the relationship between 21st-century teachers' skills and the extent of ICT integration within the new normal teaching-learning environment among junior high school teachers in the Davao City Division. Using a descriptive-correlational design, the research explored how key competencies namely, critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, and self-direction are demonstrated by educators and how these skills influence the successful incorporation of ICT in educational practices. The findings revealed that 21st-century skills were consistently and frequently practiced by teachers, with collaborative and creativity skills receiving the highest ratings. These competencies are foundational in preparing educators to meet the demands of digital transformation in education. The overall high ratings across skill domains suggest a teaching workforce that is generally well-prepared to engage in innovative, learner-centered instruction supported by modern technological tools. With regard to ICT integration, educators demonstrated strong responsiveness to using digital technologies to enhance instruction, as indicated by their favorable perceptions and effective implementation practices. Regression analysis confirmed that critical thinking and self-direction skills emerged as significant predictors of ICT integration, highlighting the importance of analytical reasoning and autonomous professional growth in driving technology adoption. While collaborative skills also showed a statistically significant influence, other domains such as communication and creativity, although positively correlated, did not reach significance thresholds. This implies that the successful use of ICT in classrooms relies particularly on educators' ability to think critically and take initiative in their professional responsibilities. In essence, the study concludes that the effectiveness of ICT integra-

tion is highly contingent upon the strength of teachers' 21st-century competencies. As education systems increasingly adapt to digital and remote modes of learning, these skills become indispensable for sustaining pedagogical relevance and responsiveness. Teachers who are reflective, innovative, and self-directed are better positioned to harness the full potential of technology in enhancing learning experiences. The study found that 21st-century teachers' skills critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, and self-direction significantly influence ICT integration in the new normal teaching-learning environment. Teachers with strong competencies in these areas are more capable of using technology effectively to create engaging, student-centered learning experiences. These findings support Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which highlights learning through observation and modeling. Teachers who model effective ICT use influence both peers and students, reinforcing the value of digital integration. Similarly, Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes active, learner-driven environments. Teachers with advanced 21st-century skills design lessons that align with constructivist principles, using ICT to foster exploration, collaboration, and deeper understanding. Thus, the integration of ICT depends not just on infrastructure but on the development of key teaching competencies. Strengthening these skills is essential to promote sustainable, effective ICT integration in today's evolving educational landscape.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration:

Learners

Learning environments should be enriched with digital tools that promote collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity. Schools must provide learners with opportunities to engage in technology-enhanced activities, enabling them to become active participants and problem-

solvers in their education. Learners should be given more responsibility in digital learning tasks to foster independence and 21st-century skills.

Teachers

Teachers should participate in continuous professional development that enhances their 21st-century competencies, particularly in critical thinking and self-direction, which have the strongest influence on ICT integration. Training should also focus on integrating ICT creatively in lesson delivery and improving communication through diverse digital media.

School Administrators

Invest in sustained ICT support by providing access to reliable technology, internet infrastructure, and technical assistance. Encourage team-teaching, lesson sharing, and digital collaboration among teachers to model and promote 21st-century competencies.

Department of Education (DepEd)

Formulate and institutionalize policies that emphasize the development and assessment of 21st-century teaching skills and ICT integration. Allocate funding and resources for technology access, teacher upskilling, and learner-centered digital innovations across schools.

Curriculum Developers

Integrate 21st-century skills and ICT-based instruction across learning areas. Curriculum designs should include projects, simulations, and digital platforms that allow both teachers and students to co-create knowledge in engaging and relevant ways.

Future Researchers

Extend this study to include longitudinal tracking of how 21st-century skills develop over time and how they continue to influence ICT integration. Future studies may also explore learners' perspectives on the effectiveness of ICT-facilitated instruction or examine these variables across different grade levels and regions.

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